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CoFe₂O₄ magnetic ceramic derived from gel and densified by spark plasma sintering

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Abstract

Cobalt ferrite (CoFe₂O₄) has been successfully synthesized by sol-gel technique. Pellets were prepared by spark plasma sintering technique (SPS) from CoFe₂O₄ sol-gel derived powder. The rapid sintering of CoFe₂O₄ pellet by SPS at 950 °C, leads to a dense ceramic (97% $\rho_{\text{theoretic}}$) with average crystallite size of 71 nm. As revealed by X-ray diffraction and Mössbauer measurements, the obtained powder and SPS pellets are spinel ferrite with a cubic symmetry. Complex dielectric investigation performed on CoFe₂O₄ ceramic reveals multiple relaxation mechanisms while the magnetic measurements indicated a saturation magnetization value of $\sim 83 \text{ A}\cdot\text{m}^2/\text{kg}$ at room temperature, which make them useful for applications in microwave domain.

Keywords: **A:** Ceramics; **B:** Sol-gel processes; Spark plasma sintering; **C:** Dielectric response;
D: Magnetic measurements

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1. Introduction

CoFe₂O₄ spinel ferrite is of high interest because of its many applications in advanced technologies e.g., lithium ion battery, high-density data storage, magnetic fluids, magnetic drug delivery, medical diagnostics, microwave devices, magneto-optics devices, sensors, high frequency applications and catalysis [1-4]. The cobalt ferrite (CoFe₂O₄) is a hard magnetic material with high coercivity (80 kA/m – 250 kA/m, depending on grain size etc.), moderate magnetization (80 A.m²/kg) and high Curie temperature (520 °C) [5,6]. Furthermore, it shows high cubic magnetocrystalline anisotropy, high magnetostrictive coefficient, great physical and chemical stability [7]. Therefore it has emerged as an important technological material being one of the most promising candidates for high-density recording media such as audio and videotape. Despite of its properties, much attention is given in the last years to the substituted cobalt ferrite with Gd, Mn, Zn, Cr, Al, etc. Moreover, recently, many synthesis of double phase multiferroic composites like CoFe₂O₄-Pb(Zr,Ti)O₃ [8] and CoFe₂O₄-BaTiO₃ [9,10] start to emerge. However, the detailed reports on cobalt ferrite pellets have not drawn enough interest so far. Only, several papers report on the structural and magnetic properties of CoFe₂O₄ sintered ceramic [11-15]. Furthermore, there is high interest in literature regarding the electrical conduction and

dielectric behaviour of these ferrites [15-19], CoFe_2O_4 ferrites being potential candidates for both magnetic and electric applications. The dielectric investigation can provide important information on the behaviour of localized electric charge carriers, giving rise to a better understanding of the mechanism of dielectric polarization. Specifically, dielectric behavior is one of the most important properties of ferrites which depend on the preparation conditions, e.g. sintering time, and temperature and heating and cooling rate [15-19]. Hence, further investigation of the CoFe_2O_4 ferrite ceramic structure evolution, dielectric, and magnetic properties is required.

The magnetic properties of the CoFe_2O_4 particles depends on their size, shape, and purity which are very sensitive to the preparation method. These particles should be nanosized, pure phase and single domain in order to improve their functional properties. For this reason, several papers report on the conditions and methods used for the preparation of cobalt ferrite nanopowders, such as: chemical co-precipitation [2], hydrothermal method, microwave synthesis, sol-gel method [20-22], complexometric method [23], polyol method [24] and others. The sol-gel route is one of the most efficient methods to prepare ultra-fine particles with a high purity and homogenous composition [23-25]. The consolidation of nanopowders to produce dense bodies while maintaining their fine crystallite size is usually difficult by conventional methods such as hot pressing, etc. Furthermore, in order to get the high magnetic performance as that of powders, avoiding detrimental effects, a highly densified pellet is necessary. Therefore, motivated by these factors, we report in the present paper the preparation of CoFe_2O_4 nanopowder and bulk by sol-gel and by SPS sintering, respectively. The aim is to obtain fine-grained sintered cobalt ferrite ceramics, with preserved or improved magnetic characteristics. The dependence of the dielectric properties and AC conductivity on frequency, at room temperature, has been investigated in details.

Furthermore, ferromagnetic properties of the ceramic are analysed by recording magnetization (M) vs. magnetic field (H) loops at different temperatures.

2. Experimental procedure

CoFe₂O₄ sol precursor was prepared starting from iron nitrate Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O (99.99%, Aldrich), cobalt acetate Co(CH₃CO₂)₂·4H₂O (99.995%, Aldrich) and citric acid monohydrate (99%, Aldrich) (C₆H₈O₇) as chelating agent. Ethanol C₂H₅OH (96.4%, Aldrich), acetic acid (99.7%) and water were used as solvents. The iron nitrate and citric acid were dissolved in ethanol separately, at room temperature. The cobalt acetate was dissolved in ethanol, acetic acid and water. Solution of iron nitrate was added to cobalt acetate solution and then, the citric acid solution was added to the mixture solutions of Fe and Co, to form a cobalt ferrite precursor sol. The molar ratio of Co:Fe:C₆H₈O₇ was 1:2:3. The as obtained sol was maintained under continuous stirring at 80 °C, for 4 h, to obtain the gel. After drying the gel at ~120 °C, the resultant powder was treated at 700 °C, 2h in air, in order to synthesize CoFe₂O₄. The as-obtained powder was sintered as discs with thickness of about 2 mm and diameter of 20 mm by spark plasma sintering technique using SPS–(FCT/Germany) equipment. To this end, the powder was poured into a graphite die and uniaxially pressed at 16 MPa using a hydraulic press. Then, the graphite die with pressed powder was introduced into SPS equipment, a pressure of 63 MPa was applied and a vacuum of 30-40 Pa is carried out. In the SPS apparatus a current pulsed pattern was applied. The waveform is composed of several spikes (pulses) separated by a current-free interval. Each pulse has the same period of about 3×10^{-3} s. In the current work, a pattern of 12:2 on: off pulses was applied. The total time of one sequence (cycle) is about 0.04 s. The operating parameters, namely voltage and the peak current were below 5 V and 1600 A, respectively. No sintering aid was added. We used a thermocouple, which was placed into horizontal channel of the die wall at 5 mm.

In Fig.1 the variation of temperature (T) and mechanical pressure (P) as a function of time, during the SPS processing of CoFe_2O_4 powder is shown.

Fig.1.

Programmed heating rate of the sample is 100 °C/min up to 900 °C, followed by an increase of temperature up to 950 °C with a heating rate of 50 °C/min. Up to 143 °C, the electrical power of SPS equipment is zero. After 5 min dwell, the electric current was turned off and the pressure was released. The CoFe_2O_4 samples densification occurs in the temperature range 560-920 °C. The presence of a thin carbon layer was observed at the surface of the as-sintered pellets, due to graphite contamination from graphite foils inserted between the die, punches and the ceramic powder. This layer was removed by polishing the surface and then, the SPS sintered pellet was annealed in oxygen, at 900 °C for 5 h in order to remove the contaminant carbon. Apparent densities of the sintered pellet was measured by Archimedes method (in water) using a density balance.

The structure of the CoFe_2O_4 powder and pellet was characterized by X-ray diffraction technique using a Bruker D8 ADVANCE diffractometer. $\text{Cu K}_{\alpha 1}$ radiation (wavelength 1.5406 Å), LiF crystal monochromator and Bragg-Brentano diffraction geometry were used. The data were acquired at 25 °C with a step-scan interval of 0.02° and a step time of 0.5 s. The XRD data were first evaluated by comparisons and searches of the International Centre for Diffraction Data (ICDD) Powder Diffraction File using Bruker AXS DIFFRAC.EVA (Bruker AXS, Karlsruhe, Germany, 2000). Room temperature Mössbauer measurements were performed with WissEL-ICE Oxford Mössbauer cryomagnetic system and a 10 mCi $^{57}\text{Co}(\text{Rh})$ source calibration. The microstructure of the obtained powder and ceramic was examined with a FEI Quanta Inspect F scanning electron microscope (SEM). The dielectric properties of the samples were studied at room temperature in 100 Hz-1 MHz range of frequency, in the metal-dielectric-metal (MFM) configuration, where the electrodes M consist of silver paste, using a 4194A Impedance/Gain-phase Analyzer. The magnetic properties of the CoFe_2O_4 powder and grinded sintered pellet were investigated using a Quantum Design

MPMS-5S SQUID magnetometer, in the temperature range of 5 K – 355 K and an applied magnetic field of up to 3580 kA/m.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. X-ray diffraction

The XRD patterns of CoFe_2O_4 calcined powders and sintered pellet are shown in Fig.2.

Fig.2.

XRD analysis showed the peaks of the partial inverted spinel cubic structure $(\text{Co}_{0.255}\text{Fe}_{0.745})[\text{Co}_{0.745}\text{Fe}_{1.255}]\text{O}_4$ with $Fd3m$ (227) space group (PDF No. 74-3419) for calcined powder and sintered pellet. The small peak at around 34° attributed to hematite Fe_2O_3 phase (PDF No. 71-5088) appeared on XRD patterns of calcined powders and sintered pellets. The reference intensity ratio (RIR) method of quantitative phase analysis, as the Rietveld one, gives results accurate to within $\sim\pm 3$ wt.% at the 95% confidence level [26]. The results of quantitative Rietveld analyses made with commercial EVA program of BRUKER are given in Table 1. It can be seen in Tab.1, that the amount of Fe_2O_3 is 8 wt.% in CoFe_2O_4 powder and 7 wt.% in sintered pellets. The average crystallite sizes were calculated using Debye Scherrer formula average crystallite size = $(k \lambda / \beta \cos\vartheta)$, where the average crystallite size is derived from the (311) peak ($2\vartheta \sim 36^\circ$) of the XRD pattern, k is the sphere shape factor ($k = 0.9$), ϑ is the Bragg's angle, β is the Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) of the peak and λ is the wavelength of X-ray ($\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$) used. The results show that the average crystallite size does not change with the SPS process and it is about 70 nm.

Tab.1.

3.5. Mössbauer analysis

The room temperature Mössbauer spectrum of CoFe_2O_4 powder exhibits a magnetic hyperfine pattern (Fig.3).

Fig.3.

In the hypothesis of Lorentzian line shape, the deconvolution reveals the presence of two magnetic sextets. It is well known [27] that in the cubic lattice of cobalt ferrite, the iron ions are located in tetrahedral and respectively octahedral positions; consequently the Mössbauer spectrum could reflect this site occupancy. The two sextets (continuous color lines in Fig.3) come from the iron ions located in tetrahedral and octahedral sites respectively. The refinement of Mössbauer spectrum was performed keeping constant the line intensities ratio as 3:2:1 - the theoretical value for polycrystalline samples. The fit parameters (isomer shift (IS), quadrupole splitting (ΔE_Q), hyperfine magnetic fields H_{hf} at the iron nucleus, line width (Γ) and relative areas (A)) are listed in Table 2.

Table 2.

The hyperfine magnetic fields at Fe nucleus of ~ 4058.4 kA/m for octahedral positions and respectively ~ 3899.3 kA/m for tetrahedral positions are characteristic for cobalt spinel structure [27]. The isomer shift values of 0.22 mm/s and 0.30 mm/s (with respect to α -iron) for tetrahedral and octahedral sites respectively are consistent with the presence of Fe^{3+} ions in cobalt ferrite; the smaller isomer shift belongs to the tetrahedral iron sites [27]).

3.2. SEM analysis

The SEM micrographs of $CoFe_2O_4$ powders show homogeneous particles and agglomerates (Fig.4(a)).

Fig.4.

SEM image of the fractured surface of a sintered pellet is shown in Fig.4(b). As can be seen, the SPS pellet consists of submicron particles and agglomerates. $CoFe_2O_4$ sintered sample shows an apparent density of 5.145 g/cm³, (97 % with respect to the theoretical value). The pellet is well sintered (many particles boundaries disappeared) but several pores

located at particles boundaries can still be observed. The structure of CoFe_2O_4 sintered ceramic by SPS is dependent on the morphology of the starting powder and their cold compaction. The agglomerates observed in the sintered cobalt ferrite (Fig.4(b)) are due to those already present in the powder used in SPS (Fig.4(a)). It is known that the agglomerates make the densification more difficult and produce an intrinsic heterogeneity in the material. In most cases, the hard agglomerates, often present in the nanopowders obtained by solution synthesis methods, do not actually break during the densification process, but just deform plastically, producing areas with density and nanopores distribution quite different from the surroundings. The result is a very dense material that presents a sort of bimodal structure. The use of very mild sintering conditions (low temperatures and short times) limit the possibility of compositional and microstructural homogenization, so the characteristics of the bulk materials obtained through SPS are significantly dependent on the characteristics of the original nanopowders [27].

3.3. Dielectric characterization

In order to understand the dielectric and conductivity behavior of sample, the complex dielectric properties were studied. The evolution with frequency (f) of the real part of the permittivity (ϵ') and losses ($\tan \delta$) for the CoFe_2O_4 ceramic, at room temperature, are presented in the Fig.5(a)-(b). The variation of real part of permittivity (ϵ') with frequency shows a decreasing trend with the increase of frequency indicating a strong dielectric dispersion (Fig.5(a)). The observed dielectric constant was 3150 at 125 Hz and 80 at 1MHz for CoFe_2O_4 sintered ceramic, with average crystallite size of 71 nm. These values of dielectric constant of CoFe_2O_4 ceramic sintered by SPS technique are higher than those reported in the literature for CoFe_2O_4 sample with average crystallite size of 50 nm, prepared by conventional sintering ($\epsilon' < 250$ at 100 Hz and 160 °C) [16]. This feature can be ascribable

to the specific morphology of the particles in ceramics sintered by SPS technique (Fig.4b).” Anyway, the results on the real part of permittivity reported here agree very well with the results reported in Refs. [15-19, 28-33]. They explain that the high values of permittivity ($\epsilon' \sim 4000$ at room temperature) in low frequency range are due to Maxwell Wagner type interfacial polarization coming from grain boundaries and surface polarization. Therefore the value of dielectric permittivity is quite controversial.

The apparent high real permittivity can be due to high losses coming from extrinsic effects (pores, grain boundaries, electrodes effects). High losses at low frequency and relaxation features in the range 10^2 – 10^3 Hz were obtained and are most probably due to pores and poor homogeneity. Anyway the ceramic still preserves losses higher than 5% for frequencies $f > 10^4$ Hz.

Fig.5.

The dielectric losses in ferrites are reflected in the conductivity measurements where the materials of high conductivity exhibit higher losses and vice-versa. When dealing with a charge carrier system, it is preferable to plot the AC complex impedance or conductivity instead of the dielectric loss for characterizing dielectric materials [15-19, 23-27, 29-33]. To understand the conduction mechanism responsible for high dielectric losses, the AC conductivity data was carried out at room temperature in the frequency range from 100 Hz to 1 MHz. The AC conductivity was calculated from the dielectric data and using the following relation:

$$\sigma_{AC} = 2\pi\epsilon_0\epsilon'(\tan \delta) f$$

where: σ_{AC} is AC conductivity of the sample ϵ_0 is the permittivity of vacuum ϵ' is the real part of the dielectric constant of the sample, $\tan \delta$ are the dielectric losses and f is the frequency of the applied field.

The conduction in ferrite can be explained by polaron hopping process among the

localized states. It is well known that in large polaron hopping the AC conductivity decreases with frequency and in small polaron hopping conductivity increases with frequency [15-19, 23-27, 30-33]. The variation of the AC conductivity with frequency (between 100 Hz and 1 MHz) for CoFe_2O_4 sintered pellets by SPS method is shown in Fig.6.

Fig.6.

The AC conductivity increases slowly at frequencies less than 10 kHz and then increases rapidly above 10 kHz indicating that the conduction occurs by small polaron hopping. As the frequency of the applied field increases, the hopping of carriers also increases; thereby increasing the conductivity. Compared with recent published results on conductivity of CoFe_2O_4 ceramics prepared with different technique [16], our values are much greater, especially at higher frequencies. This difference can be explained by a relaxation phenomenon which takes place at higher frequencies as it will be shown below by dielectric modulus formalism. Anyway, very similar results were reported recently in [15-19, 29-33]. The authors explain that electron hopping between Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} and hole hopping between Co^{2+} and Co^{3+} are responsible for the high conductivity in CoFe_2O_4 .

Impedance spectroscopy enables to explain the properties of the ferrite ceramics in relationship with their microstructures and compositions, by observing the contributions from various ceramic components (i.e. grains and grain boundaries) or from electrical interfaces (electrodes) [17, 18, 24, 25, 30-33]. The complex impedance plot from Fig.7 shows flattened semicircle with two components: the high-frequency arc is usually associated to the bulk (grain cores), while the low frequency arc to the grain boundaries contributions [17, 18, 24-25]. As can be seen from Fig.7, it is clear that almost entire spectrum of frequency (except for frequency range higher than 80 kHz) is dominated by grain boundaries contributions. The center of the first semicircular arc (from low frequency range) is depressed below the real axis indicating a high degree of heterogeneity (i.e. a broad distribution of relaxation times)

and deviation from the ideal Debye relaxation behavior. A similar behavior was reported by Panda et al. who agree that grain effects and non-Debye type relaxation dominate the electric behavior of CoFe_2O_4 at room temperature [18, 32].

Fig.7.

A better representation for understanding if multiple relaxations and/or conduction processes are involved in the complex dielectric response of the composite ceramics is given by the dielectric modulus formalism $M^*(f)$ combined with complex permittivity analysis [19, 27, 30, 32, 33]. The electric modulus is the reciprocal of the complex permittivity:

$$M^*(f) = 1/\varepsilon^*(f) = M' + iM''$$

The variation of its imaginary component M'' as a function of frequency provides useful information concerning the charge transport mechanism such as electrical transport and conductivity relaxation. A conductivity relaxation is indicated by the presence of a peak in the $M''(f)$ spectra and no peak would take place in the corresponding plot of $\tan \delta (f)$ while the dielectric relaxation gives maxima both in dielectric losses $\tan \delta (f)$ and of the dielectric modulus $M''(f)$ spectra. Comparisons of the complex $\varepsilon^*(f)$ and $M^*(f)$ representations have been used to distinguish localized dielectric relaxation processes from long-range conductivity [19, 27, 30, 32, 33]. Figure 8 shows the real and imaginary parts of electric modulus, M' and M'' , respectively, as a function of frequency, at room temperature.

Fig.8.

M' increases monotonically with increase of frequency while the imaginary part $M''(f)$ of the ceramic show one maximum in the investigated frequency range, which take place from hundreds of kHz to 1MHz. As this maximum is absent in $\tan \delta (f)$ spectra, the peak is due to a conductivity relaxation. The frequency region below peak maximum $M''(f)$ determines the range in which charge carriers are mobile on long distances At frequency above peak maximum M'' , the carriers are confined to potential wells, being mobile on short distances

[18, 19, 25, 27]. Therefore, this peak indicates the transition from long range to short range mobility with increasing frequency.

3.4. Magnetic properties

Figure 9 shows the magnetization (M) vs. magnetic field (H) of CoFe_2O_4 measured at different temperatures: 5 K, 100 K and 300 K.

Fig.9.

The saturation magnetization M_s decreases from 88 $\text{A}\cdot\text{m}^2/\text{kg}$ to 83 $\text{A}\cdot\text{m}^2/\text{kg}$ with increasing temperature from 5 K to 300 K. The value 88 $\text{A}\cdot\text{m}^2/\text{kg}$ of M_s at 5K is very close to that reported on the bulk CoFe_2O_4 (80–93 $\text{A}\cdot\text{m}^2/\text{kg}$ [34]) and higher than that recently observed on nanostructured CoFe_2O_4 obtained by SPS compaction of powder prepared by coprecipitation or thermolysis (51 $\text{A}\cdot\text{m}^2/\text{kg}$) [35]. These high values can be considered as a consequence of the contribution of the crystallites smaller than 50 nm [24] or a favourable degree of inversion in the spinel structure [36]. The dependence of the coercive field H_c on temperature of CoFe_2O_4 sintered pellet is shown in Fig.10.

Fig.10.

The coercive field is 252 kA/m at 5K and strongly decreases with increasing temperature; at room temperature, $H_c = 17.7$ kA/m. It is known that H_c becomes 0 in close proximity of the blocking temperature. By exponential extrapolation of the H_c vs. T curve to higher temperature (above 350 K, grey line), we *estimated* that H_c become zero ($H_c = 0$) at 838 K. This value matches the Curie temperature point T_c of the bulk CoFe_2O_4 (810 K) [12].

Fig.11 show the dependence of M_s , M_r and ratio M_s/M_r on temperature for CoFe_2O_4 pellet consolidated by SPS while in Table 3 the values of magnetic characteristics measured at 5 K and 300 K are presented. In Table 3 the magnetic characteristics of CoFe_2O_4 powder measured at 300 K are also shown.

Fig.11.

Table 3.

The coercivity (H_c), saturation magnetization (M_s) and remanent magnetization (M_r), of CoFe_2O_4 pellet, measured at 300 K, are 85.8 kA/m, 70 A·m²/kg and 27.2 A·m²/kg, respectively. From the results summarized in Table 3, the main difference between the magnetic characteristics of the powder and pellet is the coercivity which is superior for the powder. M_s is lower for the powder whereas M_r and M_r/M_s are slightly higher as compared to the sintered pellet. Our results on CoFe_2O_4 powder are comparable with the values reported in literature and summarized in Table 4.

Table 4.

As can be seen in Fig.11(b), the ratio of the remanent to saturation magnetizations M_r/M_s of sintered pellet in the temperature range 5 – 15 K is 0.84, which is close to value of 0.88 obtained by Meron et.al. [41] at 10K and at the same time being very close to the expected value for isolated particles with cubic anisotropy (0.83).

The relative permeability of the CoFe_2O_4 sintered ceramic by SPS was calculated as follows:

$$\mu_r = 1 + \chi \quad (1)$$

$$\chi = 4\pi\rho_m\chi_m \quad (2)$$

Where, χ is a dimensionless volumetric susceptibility, χ_m is the specific susceptibility and ρ_m is the measured density.

Figure 12 shows relative permeability vs. H curves for different temperatures of SPS sintered sample.

Fig.12.

As can be observed on Fig.12, the relative permeability (μ_r) of CoFe_2O_4 sintered pellet decreases with increase of the magnetic field (H), at constant temperature. Relative

permeability of CoFe_2O_4 sintered pellet is almost independent of temperature for magnetic field, $H > 8$ kA/m and, decreases with increasing field and temperature (Fig.13).

Fig.13.

The relative permeability is higher at higher magnetic field and room temperature, decreasing with increasing temperature. This thermal stability of the permeability in a wide range of H can find applications that require stability at relatively high magnetic fields. Generally, the magnetic permeability depends on the chemical composition and morphology of the polycrystalline material.

4. Conclusions

CoFe_2O_4 nanosized powder was prepared by sol-gel method and dense ceramic was obtained by spark plasma sintering. Average crystallite size of the densified cobalt ferrite was 71 nm. The dielectric permittivity decreases gradually as the frequency increases and becomes constant at high frequencies due to the disappearance of interfacial or space charge polarization. The loss tangent slowly decreases as the frequency increases up to 1 MHz. The AC conductivity is found to be high at higher frequencies and is due to the polaron hopping. The variation of complex impedance, electric modulus and ac conductivity with frequency indicated an ionic conduction in CoFe_2O_4 ceramic sintered by SPS method. The values of the saturation magnetization, coercive force (at room temperature) and blocking temperature for cobalt ferrite ceramic as-prepared were: $83 \text{ A}\cdot\text{m}^2/\text{kg}$, 17.7 kA/m and 838 K , respectively. Electrical conductivity, dielectric characteristics and magnetic properties of these ceramics recommend them for applications in the microwave or radio frequency range

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Figure Captions

Fig.1. Pressure and temperature vs. time for CoFe_2O_4 sample.

Fig.2. X-ray diffraction patterns of the CoFe_2O_4 powder and pellet sintered by SPS and annealed at $900\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 5 h in oxygen.

Fig.3. Room temperature Mössbauer spectrum of CoFe_2O_4 powder together with the computer fit; red line - tetrahedral sextet; blue line - octahedral sextet.

Fig.4. SEM images of CoFe_2O_4 powder, calcined at $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 2h in air (a) and of the surface of fractured CoFe_2O_4 pellet sintered by SPS at $950\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 5 min and annealed at $900\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 5 h in oxygen (b)

Fig.5. Frequency dependence of (a) real part of the permittivity and (b) imaginary part of the permittivity for CoFe_2O_4 ceramic sintered by SPS method.

Fig.6. Frequency dependence of the AC conductivity for CoFe_2O_4 ceramic sintered by SPS method.

Fig.7. Complex impedance plane plot at room temperature for CoFe_2O_4 sintered ceramic sample

Fig.8. (a) Real (M') and (b) imaginary (M'') parts of electric modulus as a function of frequency for CoFe_2O_4 ceramic sintered by SPS method

Fig.9. Magnetisation M_s for CoFe_2O_4 sintered pellet versus applied magnetic field H , measured at different temperatures (a) and detail (b).

Fig.10. Variation of the coercive force (H_c) with temperature (T) for CoFe_2O_4 sintered pellet.

Fig.11. Variation of the saturation magnetization M_s and remanent magnetization M_r (a) and the ratio of remanent to saturation magnetizations M_r/M_s (b) with temperature T for CoFe_2O_4 sintered pellet.

Fig.12. Magnetic field strength H dependence of the relative permeability μ_r for CoFe_2O_4 sintered pellet, measured at different temperatures.

Fig.13. Temperature dependence of the relative permeability (μ_r) for CoFe_2O_4 sintered pellet, at different H values.

Table Captions

Table 1. Crystalline components and CFO average crystallite size from Rietveld refinement (R_{wp} is the weighted profile residual from the Rietveld refinement).

Table 2. Mössbauer fit results for CoFe_2O_4 powder sample.

Table 3. Magnetic characteristics of CoFe_2O_4 bulk sintered by SPS and powder.

Table 4. Reported average crystallite sizes, saturation magnetization (M_s) and coercivity (H_c) for different synthesis techniques for CoFe_2O_4 powder.

Tab.1.

Crystalline components and CoFe_2O_4 average crystallite size from Rietveld refinement (R_{wp} is the weighted residual value)

Sample	CoFe_2O_4		Hematite	R_{wp}
	[wt.%]	[nm]	[wt.%]	[%]
SPS bulk	93	71	7	1.6
Powder	92	74	8	1.5

Table 2.

Mössbauer fit results for CoFe₂O₄ powder sample.

Sample	IS*	ΔE_Q	H _{hf}	Γ	Areas	Site /phase assignment
	(mm/s)	(mm/s)	(kA/m)	mm/s	(%)	
CoFe ₂ O ₄	0.212	0.039	3899.3	0.47	60.1	Tetra Fe ³⁺
	0.302	0.044	4058.4	0.58	39.9	Octa Fe ³⁺
<i>Errors</i>	± 0.002	± 0.004	± 0.05	± 0.03	± 0.4	

*IS is given relative to α -Fe.

Table 3.

Magnetic characteristics of CoFe₂O₄ bulk sintered by SPS and powder

CoFe ₂ O ₄ sample	H _c (kA/m)		M _s (A·m ² /kg)		M _r (A·m ² /kg)		M _r /M _s		μ _r (at 0.1005 T)	
	Temperature (K)									
	5	300	5	300	5	300	5	300		300
Bulk	252	17.7	88	83	74.2	21.2	0.84	0.26	6.7	
Powder	-	85.8	-	70	-	27.2	-	0.39	-	

Table 4.

Reported average crystallite sizes, saturation magnetization (M_s) and coercivity (H_c) for different synthesis techniques for CoFe_2O_4 powder

Synthesis method	Average crystallite size from XRD (nm)	Saturation magnetization ($\text{A}\cdot\text{m}^2/\text{kg}$)	Coercivity, recorded at 300 K, (kA/m)	Ref.
This paper	>100	73.5	85.78	-
Solution combustion	11	39	108.94	[37]
Hydrothermal	33	74.8	176.34	[38]
Microemulsion	50	65	114.59	[39]
Sol-gel, method 1	87	78.43	56.02	[22]
Sol-gel, method 2	74	82.78	64.78	[22]
Sol-gel autocombustion	16-26	63.53	197.19	[40]
Modified oxidation method in N_2 atmosphere	50	71	108.22	[36]
Coprecipitation	94	54.5	125.33	[41]

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Highlights

- Cobalt ferrite (CoFe_2O_4) has been processed by sol-gel and spark plasma sintering technique (SPS).
- CoFe_2O_4 ceramic shows low electrical conductivity ($\sigma_{\text{AC}} \sim 0.0022$ at 10^4 Hz and room temperature).
- CoFe_2O_4 ceramic shows complex dielectric relaxation phenomena.
- CoFe_2O_4 ceramic shows values of M_s and H_c for microwave or radio frequency devices.